

Multidomain Selective Feature Fusion and Stacking Based Ensemble Framework for EEG-Based Neonatal Sleep Stratification

Muhammad Irfan, Laishuan Wang, Husnain Shahid, Yan Xu, Abdulhamit Subasi, Adnan Munawar, Noman Mustafa, Chen Chen (*Senior member, IEEE*), Tomi Westerlund (*Senior member, IEEE*), Wei Chen (*Senior member, IEEE*)

Abstract—Employing a minimal array of electroencephalography (EEG) channels for neonatal sleep stage classification is essential for data acquisition in the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), as single-channel and edge-based features can reduce data transfer and processing requirements, enhancing cost-effectiveness and practicality. In this paper, we evaluate the efficacy of a single channel and the viability of a binary classification scheme for discerning awake and sleep states and transitions to quiet sleep. For this, two datasets of EEG signals for neonate sleep analysis were recorded from Children’s Hospital of Fudan University, Shanghai, comprising recordings from 64 and 19 neonates, respectively. From each epoch, a diverse ensemble of 490 features was extracted through a blend of discrete and continuous wavelet transforms (DWT, CWT), spectral statistics, and temporal features. In addition, we introduced an innovative hybrid univariate and ensemble feature selection approach with multidomain feature fusion, a stacking-based ensemble classifier that outperforms existing work. We achieved 90.37%, 91.13%, and 94.88% accuracy for sleep/awake, quiet sleep/non-quiet sleep, and quiet sleep/awake, respectively. This was corroborated by significant Kappa values of 77.5%, 80.29%, and 89.76%. Using SelectPercentile, we devised three distinct feature selection mechanisms: one using DWT, one with CWT, and another incorporating both spectral and temporal features. Subsequently, SelectKBest was used to determine the most effective features. For our stacked model, we incorporated a trifecta of the ExtraTree model with variable estimators, a Random Forest, and an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) as base classifiers, and for the final prediction phase, ANN was implemented again. The model’s performance was evaluated using K-fold and leave-one-subject cross-validation.

Index Terms—Multidomain Selective Feature Fusion, Stacking Based Ensemble Model, EEG, IoMT, Single Channel Analysis, Neonatal Sleep.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) revolutionizes healthcare by enabling remote monitoring and diagnosis, reducing costs, and

This work is supported by Shanghai Municipal Science and Technology International R&D Collaboration Project (Grant No. 20510710500), The Finnish National Agency for Education (Grant No. OPH-3323-2023), and FCFH Support Funding for 2024—Grants.

Muhammad Irfan is affiliated with CIME, Fudan University, Shanghai, and the University of Turku, Finland, including the TIERS Group, Turku PET Center, and Turku University Hospital (imuhammad18@fudan.edu.cn, muhammad.m.irfan@utu.fi). Yan Xu and Laishuan Wang are with the National Children’s Medical Center, Children’s Hospital of Fudan University, Shanghai, China (xuyan-fimmu@163.com), (laishuanwang@163.com). Abdulhamit Subasi is with the University at Albany, USA, and Effat University, Saudi Arabia (asubasi@albany.edu). Chen Chen is with the Human Phenome Institute, Fudan University, Shanghai, China (chenchen_fd@fudan.edu.cn). Husnain Shahid is a Researcher at Centre Tecnològic de Telecommunicacions de Catalunya, Spain (hshahid@cttc.es). Noman Mustafa is with MetronHK Vision Technology (an Apple subsidiary), China (noman.mustafa@sytu.edu.cn). Adnan Munawar is with Tianjin University, China (adnanmunawar@tju.edu.cn). Tomi Westerlund is with the University of Turku, Finland (tovewe@utu.fi). Wei Chen (corresponding author) is with the University of Sydney, Australia (wei.chenbme@sydney.edu.au).

improving accessibility [1], [2]. IoMT enhances precision and reliability in health monitoring, particularly with fewer-channel electroencephalography (EEG) devices used for neonatal sleep studies [1]. This not only reduces the burden on healthcare systems but also provides a powerful tool for gathering critical data on neonatal sleep patterns. By analyzing large datasets with machine learning (ML) models, researchers can pinpoint healthy sleep patterns and effectively identify potential sleep disorders in neonates [1].

Neonates spend a lot of time sleeping because it’s essential for their well-being [3]. During sleep, their rapidly developing brains are busy storing memories, and their bodies are growing [3]. Sleep also strengthens their immune system, making them better prepared to fight illness. Awake periods in neonates involve alertness and responsiveness to the environment, quiet sleep is defined by minimal physical activity and slower brain patterns, and active sleep is where most dreaming occurs, marked by rapid eye movements and increased brain activity, crucial for brain development [4].

Analyzing sleep patterns during neonatal development is essential to detect sleep apnea and neurological disorders that can impact brain development and growth [5]. EEG devices provide valuable insights into sleep stages, allowing early intervention to improve neonatal health. Understanding these stages helps caregivers anticipate sleep and wakefulness patterns, potentially reducing the risk of sudden infant death syndrome (SIDS) and accidental suffocation and strangulation in bed (ASSB) [6].

The EEG signals of neonates differ from those of adults, with lower frequencies, higher amplitudes, and slower wave activity, complicating the monitoring of their health [7]. Rapid brain growth in neonates yields frequent EEG pattern changes, making consistent classification challenging. Artifacts such as muscle movements along with equipment noise exacerbate this challenge [8], [9]. The nebulous transitions between neonatal sleep stages and the lack of standard recording and analysis methods further complicate and impede data quality and interpretability [9]. To mitigate these concerns, researchers employ advanced signal processing, ML, and deep learning (DL) strategies [10]–[13]. These approaches effectively extract salient EEG signal features, eliminate artifacts, and discern patterns that differentiate sleep stages. In addition, creating standardized recording and analysis protocols is a promising step toward enhancing the accuracy and reliability of neonatal sleep stage classification.

Our study investigated the performance of various ML classifiers when applied as ensemble models, stacking models, and voting models. We evaluated quadratic discriminant analysis (QDA), K-nearest neighbors (KNN) classifier, support vector machine (SVM), gaussian naive bayes (GNB), decision tree, multi-layer perceptron (MLP), random forest (RF), Adaboost. We also considered ensemble approaches including bagging ensemble model (BEM) and extra trees classifier (ETC). Furthermore, we explored stacking models, one combining KNN, MLP, and RF as estimators, and another using RF, extra trees classifiers (ETCI, ETCII, ETCIII), and artificial neural networks (ANN) as estimators.

Main contributions of our work are as follows: The article’s key contributions include:

- 1) We present a novel approach for multidomain selective feature fusion and dimensionality reduction (MMFFS), combining hybrid univariate and ensemble methods to improve feature selection and fusion efficiency.
- 2) We present a novel ensemble-based stacking model. This classifier, the result of careful experimentation, combines the strengths of three robust ML ensemble models: a trifacta of comprising ETC models with variable estimators, RFC, and ANN serving as base classifiers. Furthermore, for the final prediction phase, we exclusively employed an ANN.
- 3) Using a single channel, we propose an IoT-based architecture to reduce data transfer for cloud storage, while simultaneously extracting key features at the edge.
- 4) Demonstrating the efficacy and accuracy of our approach in distinguishing between sleep versus awake (SvA), quiet sleep versus awake (QvA), and quiet sleep vs non-quiet sleep (QvQ_n) using a single channel, thereby establishing its potential and reliability in neonatal sleep stage analysis.

This manuscript unfolds as follows: Section II provides an overview of the pertinent literature. The methodology, encompassing feature extraction, hybrid univariate, and ensemble feature selection approaches, multi-domain feature fusion, and classifier deployment, is detailed in Section III. Section IV elucidates an ablation study, illustrating the proposed approach's effectiveness in classifying neonatal sleep stages and how the proposed methodology is developed. The findings with discussion are delineated in Section V. Finally, Section VI summarizes the study's findings and highlights potential directions for future exploration.

II. RELATED WORK

ML and DL-based neonatal sleep staging solutions offer an automated, reliable method to analyze EEG data [14]. They assist in precise sleep stage classification, thus aiding in the diagnosis and treatment of potential neonatal neurological or developmental issues [15]. In an important development, Awais et al. achieved outstanding accuracy in neonatal sleep classification using a diffusion-convolutional neural network (DCNN) and a SVM model [10]. Nevertheless, their dependence on video EEG data raises privacy issues [16], [17]. Meanwhile, in [18], Amir et al. implemented an improved Sinc-based DL model that effectively classified quiet sleep using only EEG data, but at the cost of greater computational requirements., limiting its use in IoMT applications. Contributing to the field further, Ansari et al. designed an 18-layer convolutional neural network (CNN) to distinguish quiet sleep from non-quiet sleep [19]. The researchers then developed a multi-scale deep CNN using a novel Sinc block for temporal feature extraction across a range of timescales [20]. Similarly, Rui et al. automated neonatal sleep state classification using single-channel EEG datasets [21]. Fraiwan et al. employed long short-term memory (LSTM) to classify neonatal sleep stages, analyzing EEG data from 16 full-term neonates [11]. Hangyu et al. designed a novel multi-scale hierarchical neural network (MS-HNN) for neonatal sleep classification [22] and resulted in around 76.5% accuracy for three-stage classification.

A. Comparative Analysis of Proposed Method and Pre-existing Research

Table I provides a comparison for the SvA classification, where previous studies using multi-channel EEG data from datasets from Children Hospital, Fudan University, Shanghai, China (FDU-19 & FDU-64) details given in section III-B, have reported accuracies ranging between 71.00% and 87.56%, with kappa scores ranging

from 52.00% to 74.36%. A significant study by Siddiqua *et al.* [23] reported an accuracy of 84.78% using 9 channels from the FDU-19 dataset. In contrast, our proposed methodology demonstrates a significant improvement. With a single channel, it achieves 86.74% accuracy on the FDU-19 dataset and 90.12% on the FDU-64 dataset.

TABLE I: Performance Comparison for SvA Classification

Study	Ch	Dataset	Validation Method	Accuracy	Kappa
[23]	9	FDU-19	Random split	84.78	69.63
[24]	9	FDU-19	Random split	82.53	65.00
[24]	4	FDU-19	Random split	74.70	55.00
[25]	9	FDU-19	Random split	85.66	69.00
[26]	1	FDU-19	5-Fold-CV	77.50	55.00
[27]	2	FDU-19	7-Fold-CV	87.56	74.13
This Study	1	FDU-19	5-Fold-CV	86.76	74.50
This Study	1	FDU-64	5-Fold-CV	90.37	77.56

As outlined in Table II, previous studies into QvA classification have reported accuracy within the range of 91.00% to 94.63%, with kappa scores ranging from 71.00% to 83.87%. When limited to one or two channels with 5 fold cross-validation (CV), our methodological approach achieved 95.80% accuracy on FDU-19 and 94.14% accuracy on FDU-64, with kappa scores of 84.19% and 88.28%, respectively. When employing the leave-one-subject-out cross-validation (LOSO-CV) method on FDU-19 with our proposed methodology, our model attained an accuracy of 92.88% and a kappa value of 79.76%.

TABLE II: Performance Comparison for QvA Classification

Study	Ch	Dataset	Validation Method	Accuracy	Kappa
[25]	9	FDU-19	Random split	94.27	73.00
[27]	2	FDU-19	7-Fold-CV	94.63	83.87
[28]	9	FDU-19	LOSO-CV	91.00	71.00
This Study	2	FDU-19	5-Fold-CV	95.80	84.19
This Study	2	FDU-19	LOSO-CV	92.88	79.76

Prior QvQ_n classification (Table III) achieved 86.00% accuracy and 75.00-77.00% kappa scores. Our strategy surpasses this with 89.18% (LOSO-CV) and 91.13% (5-Fold-CV) accuracy, along with kappa scores of 77.13% (LOSO-CV) to 79.69% (5-Fold-CV).

TABLE III: Performance Comparison for QvQ_n Classification. Helsinki University Children's Hospital, Finland (HUFU), University Hospitals Leuven, Belgium (UHLB)

Study	Ch	Dataset	Validation Method	Accuracy	Kappa
[8]	4	HUFU	LOSO-CV	86.00	76.00
[20]	8	UHLB	Fixed split	–	77.00
[20]	1	UHLB	Fixed split	–	75.00
This Study	1	FDU-64	5-Fold-CV	91.13	79.69
This Study	1	FDU-64	LOSO-CV	89.18	77.13

Our methodology introduces an efficient, single-channel approach. By using edge-based feature extraction and selecting 75 key features per epoch, coupled with stacking model, we propose a innovative approach for neonatal sleep classification. This improved approach is set to improve the IoMT domain by expediting processing times.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fig. 1: Study Overview.

A. Study Flowchart

The flowchart shown in Fig 1 presents a simplified description of the study methodology, outlining the progression from the initial level to the final stage.

B. Dataset

A total of 83 neonates (64+19) were enrolled in this study from the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) of Children's Hospital, Fudan University, Shanghai, China. This research protocol was reviewed and approved by the Children's Hospital Research Ethics Committee (Approval number: (2017) 89).

1) **Dataset-1**: Dataset-1 consisted of 64 infants, with an equal distribution of 32 boys and 32 girls. The average gestational age at birth was 38.3 weeks (± 1.8), and the postmenstrual age during data collection was 40.5 weeks (± 1.7). The infants had an average weight of 3.3 kg (± 0.6). The study observed sleep durations averaging 86.5 minutes (± 34.4), while wakefulness periods lasted approximately 43.0 minutes (± 34.5) on average. The criteria for inclusion in the research incorporated multiple factors such as hyperbilirubinemia, sepsis, and other relevant conditions. Physiological EEG data gathered from the infants for analysis included signals from several channels: Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, C3, C4, P3, P4, T3, and T4, along with a reference channel Cz. In addition, electrooculography (EOG), electromyography (EMG), and electrocardiography (ECG) signals were also recorded. The Nicolet device was deployed for data acquisition, using a sampling rate of 500 Hz. Expert neonatologists specializing in neonatal sleep stages manually classified the sleep stages of newborns, based on the recorded physiological signals. In order to assess the effectiveness of the proposed methodologies, this manual classification was used as a reference standard.

2) **Dataset-2**: Nineteen neonates were recorded using a 10–20 electrode system over an average duration of 120 minutes, capturing at least one sleep cycle per neonate in dataset-2 (FDU-19). Our analysis focused primarily on ten specific electrode channels: F3-C3 (C1), C3-P3 (C2), F4-C4 (C3), C4-P4 (C4), F3-T3 (C5), T3-P3 (C6), F4-T4 (C7), T4-P4 (C8), T3-C3 (C9), and C4-T4 (C10). In our study, we prioritized the channel that yielded the best results. A detailed description of the dataset and its annotation can be found in our preceding work [10], [24], [25].

C. Preparation of Data

A three-step pre-processing methodology was used to remove noise and artifacts from the EEG data, sampled at 500 Hz. In the first stage, a finite impulse response (FIR) filter was applied with high-pass (HP) and low-pass (LP) parameters set at 0.3 Hz and 35 Hz respectively, utilizing the advanced filtering capabilities of EEGLAB [29]. This step facilitates the removal of unwanted frequency ranges. As a second stage, the comprehensive EEG data were segmented into 30-second epochs, labeled for easy identification, and broken down into manageable segments. In the final stage of preprocessing, signal denoising with multi-scale principal component analysis (MSPCA) is carried out [30].

D. Multidomain Feature Extraction

Neonates have significantly different brainwave patterns compared to adults due to their ongoing brain development. However, manually extracted features, as described in [31], [32], often fail to capture consistently important characteristics needed for accurate sleep stage detection. Automatic sleep stage detection also faces challenges such as limited data availability [33], unclear data representations, and detection methods with low precision. To overcome these limitations and achieve accurate and precise sleep stage detection, advanced feature extraction methods are crucial. In this study, we analyzed each epoch to extract a comprehensive set of features, including 490 features from each individual channel.

1) **Discrete Wavelet Transform**: The discrete wavelet transform (DWT) analyzes the time-frequency properties of signals [34]. This involves decomposing a signal, denoted as “y,” into a linear combination of translations and dilations of a basis function known as “Mother Wavelet,” along with a scaling function. DWT involves filtering the signal using LP and HP filters, resulting in approximate coefficients (A) and detailed coefficients (D). For the next level of approximate and detailed coefficients, these coefficients are then down-sampled and the process is repeated iteratively. The iterative process establishes time-scale regions instead of time-frequency regions for the signal.

Standard quadrature mirror filter conditions establish the criteria for constructing the LP filter, designated as g , which is used to define any wavelet transformed functions. It is defined by:

$$G(z)G(z^{-1}) + G(-z)G(-z^{-1}) = 1 \quad (1)$$

Here, $G(z)$ represents the z-transform of the filter g . The corresponding HP filter, denoted as $H(z)$, can be expressed as:

$$H(z) = zG(-z^{-1}) \quad (2)$$

A sequence of filters, indexed by i and with increasing length, can be derived from (3) and (4):

$$G_{i+1}(z) = G(z^{2^i})G_i(z) \quad (3)$$

$$H_{i+1}(z) = H(z^{2^i})G_i(z), \quad i = 0, \dots, I - 1 \quad (4)$$

The initial condition is given as $G_0(z) = 1$. These equations establish a two-scale relation in the time domain:

$$g_{i+1}(k) = [g]_{\uparrow 2^i} g_i(k), \quad h_{i+1}(k) = [h]_{\uparrow 2^i} g_i(k) \quad (5)$$

where the subscript $[\cdot]_{\uparrow m}$ denotes up-sampling by a factor of m , while k represents the uniformly sampled discrete time. The normalized wavelet and scale basic functions, $\phi_{i,l}(k)$ and $\psi_{i,l}(k)$ can be defined as follows:

$$\phi_{i,l}(k) = 2^{i/2} g_i(k - 2^i l) \quad (6)$$

$$\psi_{i,l}(k) = 2^{i/2} h_i(k - 2^i l) \quad (7)$$

In this case, the factor $2^{i/2}$ serves as an inner product normalization, while i and l represent the scale and translation parameters, respectively. The DWT decomposition can be characterized as follows:

$$a_{(i)}(l) = x(k) * \phi_{i,l}(k) \quad (8)$$

$$d_{(i)}(l) = x(k) * \psi_{i,l}(k) \quad (9)$$

where $a_i(l)$ and $d_i(l)$ represent the approximation coefficients and the detail coefficients at resolution i , respectively [27].

In the DWT, two filters are used for HP and LP filtering of the time-domain signal: the discrete mother wavelet filter ($h[\cdot]$) and its counterpart, the scaling function ($g[\cdot]$). The process results in outputs (Di and Ai) that are down-sampled, with the initial approximation being decomposed into A2 and D2 iteratively. A2 further decomposes into D3 and A3, and so on. The application of DWT in signal analysis hinges on the selection of suitable wavelets and the determination of optimal decomposition levels, mindful of preserving signal frequencies essential for classification. For neonatal EEG signal analysis, which usually omits frequencies over 30 Hz- we selected 7 decomposition levels to capture crucial frequencies for accurate classification. Hence, the EEG signals break down into seven detail coefficients (D1-D7) and a final approximation coefficient (A7) [35], [36]. Finding the most fitting wavelet typically involves experimenting with various types. Our investigation into changes in EEG signals determined that the Daubechies wavelet of order 4 (db4) enhanced the classification performance of these signals [36].

Features Derived from DWT: The db4 filter's frequency response has a single band with a cut-off frequency at half of the sampling rate, which means the maximum frequency in the EEG signal will be 250 Hz. Decomposing a signal with the db4 wavelet produces multiple levels, each representing a unique frequency band [27]. The frequency bands at each level can be determined using the following formula:

$$f = (k/(2^j)) * Fs \quad (10)$$

where f is the frequency, k an integer between 0 and $2^{(j-1)} - 1$, j the level of decomposition, and Fs the sampling frequency in Hz .

It should be noted that the frequency bands for the approximation and detail coefficients complement each other. Specifically, the detail band at level j corresponds to the approximation band at level $j + 1$, and the approximation band at level 7 represents the entire signal (in this case). To represent the time-frequency distribution of EEG signals, the study used the following statistical features:

- 1) The mean of the absolute values of coefficients in each sub-band.
- 2) The median of coefficients in each sub-band.
- 3) The root mean square values of each sub-band.
- 4) The standard deviation of coefficients in each sub-band.
- 5) The ratio of absolute mean values of adjacent sub-bands.
- 6) The skewness of each sub-band.
- 7) The kurtosis of each sub-band.

2) Continuous Wavelet Transform: The continuous wavelet transform (CWT) is a powerful mathematical tool used for analyzing signals in both the time and frequency domains. It allows for a localized representation of a signal's frequency content, capturing both high and low-frequency components at different scales and positions. The CWT is based on a mother wavelet function $\psi(t)$, which acts as a prototype for analyzing the signal. By scaling and translating the wavelet function, we obtain different versions of the wavelet $\psi_{a,b}(t)$, where a represents the scale parameter and b represents the translation parameter [37].

The wavelet function $\psi(t)$ is selected to satisfy certain admissibility conditions, ensuring that it can adequately analyze signals [37]. It can be scaled and translated using the scale parameter a and translation parameter b to obtain the scaled and translated wavelet $\psi_{a,b}(t)$ given by the equation:

$$\psi_{a,b}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \psi\left(\frac{t-b}{a}\right) \quad (11)$$

where the scale parameter a controls the width of the wavelet function, allowing analysis at different frequencies. The translation parameter b determines the position of the wavelet function along the time axis, enabling analysis at different positions.

The CWT is computed by convolving the signal $x(t)$ with the complex conjugate of the scaled and translated wavelet function [38]. This convolution process measures the similarity between the signal and the wavelet at different scales and positions. The CWT can be expressed by (12).

$$CWT(a, b) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x(t) \cdot \psi_{a,b}^*(t) dt \quad (12)$$

where $CWT(a, b)$ represents the CWT coefficient at scale a and position b . The integral sums up the products of the signal and the wavelet at different time instants, capturing the similarity between the signal and the wavelet at different scales and positions.

By selecting an appropriate wavelet function, scaling it to different frequencies and translating it to different positions, and convolving it with the signal, the CWT allows for the analysis of localized time and frequency information. The CWT provides a powerful framework for signal analysis, offering advantages in capturing both high and low-frequency components and adapting to varying signal characteristics. The research utilized similar features in CWT as in DWT to represent the time-frequency distribution of EEG signals, excluding the aspect of the ratio of absolute mean values of adjacent sub-bands.

Steps for Feature Extraction using CWT:

- 1) Define the wavelet type as signal.morlet.
- 2) Set the sampling frequency (Fs) to 500 Hz .

- 3) Calculate the Nyquist frequency (f_{nyquist}) by dividing the sampling frequency by 2:

$$f_{\text{nyquist}} = \frac{Fs}{2}$$

- 4) Set the minimum frequency (f_{min}) to 1 and the maximum frequency (f_{max}) to 35.
- 5) Define the number of scales (num_scales) as 32.
- 6) Compute the corresponding scales based on the wavelet and Nyquist frequency:
- 7) Create an empty DataFrame to hold the calculated features.
- 8) Iterate over each signal: Compute the CWT using the Morlet wavelet and the scales.
- 9) Iterate over each sub-band in the CWT matrix
- 10) Convert the complex numbers in the sub-band to the magnitude and phase
- 11) Calculate the metrics, such as mean, median, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis, rms for both magnitude and phase.
- 12) Store the calculated metrics in the DataFrame with appropriate column names.
- 13) Repeat the above steps for each signal and each sub-band.

3) Temporal and Spectral Features: Analysis of neonatal sleep patterns from EEG signals relies heavily on time-domain and spectral features. Eleven temporal features were extracted for each EEG epoch, including mean amplitude, standard deviation, peak-to-peak amplitude, variance, square root, minimum amplitude, maximum amplitude, root mean square (RMS), skewness, and kurtosis. These features capture the statistical properties of the EEG signal in the time domain. Furthermore, EEG signals exhibit distinct frequency components associated with various sleep stages, cognitive processes, and emotional states. These frequency components are typically categorized into four bands: α , β , θ , and δ . Spectral features were computed for each frequency band, mirroring the temporal features (excluding absolute mean change in amplitude). This resulted in a total of forty features, collectively referred to as "Spectral Statistics of Four Bands." These spectral features provide insights into the amplitude and variability within each specific frequency range, enabling the analysis of the relationship between EEG frequency bands and sleep states.

4) The Importance of Feature Selection : EEG signal feature selection is a key step in neonatal sleep classification. In addition, it reduces the dimensionality of the data and improves the accuracy of the classification algorithms. Furthermore, it makes algorithms faster and more efficient by reducing computational complexity, which is very critical for IoMT systems. SelectKBest and SelectPercentile are two popular techniques for feature selection. SelectKBest selects the k highest-scoring features from train data based on a chosen scoring function. The scoring function, denoted as $s(x, y)$, can be any function that evaluates the importance of each feature. For example, in classification tasks, one common scoring function is the chi-squared statistic. The chi-squared statistic for feature x and target y is computed as follows:

$$\chi^2(x, y) = \sum_i \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i} \quad (13)$$

where O_i is the observed count and E_i is the expected count of class i .

SelectPercentile, on the other hand, selects features that fall into the user-defined top percentile of highest scores according to the scoring function. It functions similarly to SelectKBest, but a percentage is provided instead of specifying the number of features. The features from train data whose scores fall in the top $p\%$ of all scores are

selected. If $s(x, y)$ is the scoring function as before, then a feature x is selected if:

$$s(x, y) \geq \text{Percentile}_p(s(X, y)) \quad (14)$$

where $s(X, y)$ is the array of scores for all features, and $\text{Percentile}_p(s(X, y))$ is the score below which a given percentage p of the scores fall.

5) Multidomain Selective Feature Fusion and Dimension Reduction: To achieve efficient feature selection and dimensionality reduction, we employ a multi-stage approach that utilize both domain-specific knowledge and ensemble methods while considering inter-domain feature correlations.

a) Domain-Specific Selection with SelectPercentile: We begin by applying `SelectPercentile` independently within each feature domain (DWT, CWT, and temporal-spectral). This approach preserves a specific percentage of train features based on their highest ANOVA F-values, ensuring the inclusion of informative features pertinent to each domain. For example, it retains 46 features from DWT, 19 features from CWT, and 15 features from temporal-spectral analysis. Such domain-specific selection can also indirectly capture certain inter-domain relationships. By focusing on informative features within each domain, we capture characteristics that might be influenced by or influence features in other domains. For instance, selecting features related to slow wave activity in the DWT domain might indirectly capture some information about sleep stages, which are also reflected in temporal features. However, it doesn't directly address correlations across domains. In particular, previous research found that `SelectPercentile` and `SelectKBest` were more effective for dimensionality reduction and feature selection than PCA in the context of neonatal EEG data [27].

b) Feature Concatenation: Following domain-specific selection, the chosen features from each domain are concatenated, forming a unified feature set that incorporates valuable information from different domains.

c) Statistical Refinement with SelectKBest:: To further refine the feature set and potentially capture more complex inter-domain relationships, we fit `SelectKBest` function on the combined train feature set after concatenation and transform the test data. This method selects the top 75 features based on their statistical significance in the context of all features, potentially identifying features that bridge across domains and contribute significantly to classification accuracy.

d) Extra Trees Classifier for Feature Importance:: While not directly used for feature selection in this specific step, the `ExtraTreesClassifier` employed within the stacking ensemble can provide valuable insights into feature importance. By analyzing these importance scores, we can gain further understanding of which features, potentially including those that bridge across domains are most influential for the overall classification task.

By combining these techniques, we achieve a framework that promotes high predictive accuracy, prevents overfitting, and leverages both domain-specific knowledge and ensemble methods for effective feature selection and dimensionality reduction.

E. Classifiers

This study involved evaluating and comparing various ensemble ML, stacking, and voting classifiers, with a focus on the ETC, which exhibited the best performance. To further enhance performance, we developed a stacking-based ensemble model. This model incorporated three instances of the ETC, RF, and ANN as base models. In addition, ANN was implemented as the final estimator. The selected models were determined based on their superior performance during the

experiment. By integrating these models into the proposed ensemble stacking approach, we aimed to optimize predictive accuracy and improve overall system performance.

1) *Ensemble ExtraTreesClassifier*: The ETC model, widely employed in ML, enhances classification models' accuracy and robustness by combining multiple decision trees. At each node, a subset of features is chosen, and random splitting is employed to construct several decision trees. This approach reduces their correlation and mitigates the risk of overfitting. The algorithm combines the information of all trees, taking into account their individual strengths and weaknesses, to generate the final classification.

It utilizes Gini impurity and Information Gain for data splitting and tree creation. Gini impurity quantifies the impurity of a single node within a decision tree by assessing the probability of misclassifying a randomly selected sample within that node, assuming random labeling based on the class distribution within the node. A lower Gini impurity signifies a more homogeneous node, where the majority of samples belong to the same class. The Gini impurity is computed using the following formula:

$$\text{Gini_impurity} : i_G(p) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^x (p_i)^2 \quad (15)$$

where p_i is the proportion of samples in the node that belongs to the i_{th} class, and x belongs to the total number of classes.

$$\text{Entropy} = i_H(p) = - \sum_{i=1}^x (p_i) \log_2(p_i + \epsilon) \quad (16)$$

where ϵ is the small constant to avoid taking the algorithm of 0. To select the best features to split the data, the ETC model uses:

$$G(T, f) = \sum_N^{N_{left}} (i_{left}) + \sum_N^{N_{right}} (i_{right}) \quad (17)$$

$$\Delta i(s, j) = i(s) - \frac{N_{left}}{N} i(s_{left}) - \frac{N_{right}}{N} i(s_{right}) \quad (18)$$

where $\Delta i(s, j)$ represents the impurity reduction of split j on node s , $i(s)$ represents the impurity of node s , N_{left} and N_{right} represent the number of samples in the left and right child nodes after the split, N represents the total number of samples in the node before the split, and $i(s_{left})$ and $i(s_{right})$ represent the impurity of the left and right child nodes after the split. To predict the class label for a new sample, ETC computes the majority vote of all the decision trees.

Information Gain I_G is a measure of the reduction in entropy (i.e., the degree of disorder) of a set of samples that results from splitting them according to a particular feature. It is defined as:

$$I_G = Entropy_{parent} - \text{weightedaverageEntropy}_{children} \quad (19)$$

where $Entropy_{parent}$ is the entropy of the parent node, and $Entropy_{children}$ is the entropy of the child nodes resulting from the split.

2) *Stacking-Based Ensemble Model*: ETC is an ensemble learning method that is particularly effective in handling high-dimensional data. RF, another ensemble technique, is known for its ability to manage variance and overfitting by averaging multiple de-correlated trees. On the other hand, ANNs excel in capturing complex, non-linear relationships. In our stacking model, ETC, RF, and ANN serve as the base classifiers, while ANN in addition to that also acts as the final estimator. The output of the base classifiers is used as input to the ANN. The ANN is trained to effectively combine the predictions of the base classifiers to make a final decision. The

flow of the ensemble-based stacking model with K-fold is shown in Fig 2. A decision tree makes predictions by traversing the tree from the root to a leaf based on feature splits. The criterion for a split in the decision tree is usually the maximization of information gain, or equivalently, the minimization of impurity. Gini impurity is often employed in the case of classification tasks, and is given in (15).

In ANN, the output of a neuron is computed using weights, biases, and an activation function as given in (20).

$$a = f \left(\sum_{i=1}^n w_i x_i + b \right) \quad (20)$$

where a is the output of the neuron, f is the activation function, w_i denotes the weights, x_i represents the inputs, b is the bias term, and n is the number of inputs. The pseudocode for the proposed model is presented in the algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Stacking Ensemble Classification

```

1: procedure STACKING( $X_{train}, y_{train}, X_{test}, y_{test}, k$ )
2:    $ann \leftarrow$  MLPClassifier( $hidden\_layer\_sizes =$ 
   ( $100, \dots$ ),  $activation = 'relu'$ )
3:    $et1 \leftarrow$  ExtraTreesClassifier( $n\_estimators =$ 
    $100, max\_features = k$ )
4:    $et2 \leftarrow$  ExtraTreesClassifier( $n\_estimators =$ 
    $200, max\_features = k$ )
5:    $et3 \leftarrow$  ExtraTreesClassifier( $n\_estimators =$ 
    $300, max\_features = k$ )
6:    $rf \leftarrow$  RandomForestClassifier()
7:    $base\_classifiers \leftarrow [(et1), (et2), (et3), (rf), (ann)]$ 
8:    $stacking\_model \leftarrow$  StackingClassifier( $estimators =$ 
    $base\_classifiers, final\_estimator = ann$ )
9:    $stacking\_model.fit(X_{train}, y_{train})$ 
10:   $scores \leftarrow$  cross_val_score( $stacking\_model,$ 
    $X_{train}, y_{train}, cv = k = 5$ )
11:  Print cross-validation scores
12:   $stacking\_predictions \leftarrow$   $stacking\_model.predict(X_{test})$ 
13:  Calculate and print accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score,
   Cohen's Kappa, and Matthews correlation coefficient
14:  Print classification report and confusion matrix
15: end procedure

```

IV. ABLATION STUDY

To determine the most effective methods for classifying neonatal sleep, a comprehensive series of experiments were conducted. In conjunction with different feature extraction methods, ensemble models, stacking, and voting were systematically evaluated. As a result, four approaches were determined to offer satisfactory performance when utilized with ML models. To further enhance feature selection, a MMFFS was employed as discussed in section III-D.5. Based on this approach, 75 features out of 490 distinct features derived from different extraction methods were identified and fed into the models.

A. Assessing the Effectiveness of Each Feature Extraction Method with Stacking-Based Ensemble Model

Fig 3 shows that SvA, QvA, and QvQ_n detection can be achieved most accurately and efficiently using MMFFS. It is followed by the DWT method, which exhibits the second-best performance. T&F method shows slightly lower performance but still maintains reasonably high accuracy and kappa values; however, the CWT method has the lowest performance of all. Based on each method evaluation metric, we defined the percentile value to perform the best feature selection using SelectPercentile.

Fig. 2: Stacking-Based Ensemble Model

Fig. 3: Performance Analysis of Feature Extraction Methods for SvA, QvA, and QvQ_n Detection using Stacking Ensemble Model

B. The Importance of Multidomain Selective Feature Fusion and Dimensionality Reduction

Two feature fusion and dimension reduction methodologies were employed in this study: multidomain feature fusion (MMFF) and multidomain selective feature fusion and dimension reduction (MMFFS). MMFFS is described in detail in Section III-D.5. MMFF involves feature extraction from different domains, followed by concatenation using feature fusion. Dimensionality reduction is then achieved using a selectKbest approach, as implemented in prior studies [27].

Compared to MMFF, MMFFS offers several advantages. It significantly reduces the number of samples (by 50%), minimizing data transmission to the cloud. Additionally, it enhances classification accuracy and facilitates localized feature fusion, optimizing network resources and reducing computational costs due to the decreased number of data points. The efficacy of these methods for neonatal sleep classification was evaluated experimentally as shown in Table IV. This approach effectively reduces the number of samples, requiring fewer samples per epoch for model training and testing.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, we introduced a novel approach to sleep state classification through a MMFFS method, coupled with a stacking ensemble framework. The efficacy of this framework was evaluated by classifying various sleep states and wakefulness, specifically

Method	SvA		QvA		QvQ _n	
	Acc	Kappa	Acc	Kappa	Acc	Kappa
MMFF	87.79	71.88	92.66	85.31	88.66	74.27
MMFFS	90.37	77.51	94.88	89.76	91.13	80.29

TABLE IV: (MMFF & Stacking Ensemble Model) vs (MMFFS & Stacking Ensemble Model): K=75

focusing on neonatal subjects. The results, detailed in Tables V, VI, and VII, highlight the superior performance of our proposed model across multiple metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, cohen's kappa (Kappa), and matthews correlation coefficient (MCC). For the SvA classification, the stacking model achieved an accuracy of 90.37%, significantly outperforming individual models such as the Decision Tree, ETC, Bagging, RF, and AdaBoost. Similar enhancements in performance were observed in the QvA sleep classification, where the stacking model recorded an impressive accuracy of 94.88%. In the differentiation between QvQ_n, the stacking model also demonstrated robust classification capabilities with an accuracy of 91.13%.

TABLE V: Comparative Performance Analysis of Fine Tuned ML Models and Stacking Model for SvA Using Selective Features Fusion. Channel: T4REF. Dataset-FDU-64

Model	Acc	Precision	Recall	F1	Kappa	MCC
Decision Tree	82.37	82.42	82.37	82.39	60.36	60.36
ETC	89.51	89.48	89.51	89.32	75.59	75.93
Bagging	87.16	87.14	87.16	86.83	69.76	70.37
RF	88.77	88.75	88.77	88.54	73.75	74.19
Adaboost	87.16	87.02	87.16	87.04	70.56	70.65
Stacking Model	90.37	90.22	90.31	90.24	77.51	77.56

TABLE VI: Comparative Performance Analysis of Fine Tuned ML Models and Stacking Model for QvA Leveraging Selective Features Fusion. Channel: T4REF. Dataset-FDU-64

Model	Acc	Precision	Recall	F1	Kappa	MCC
Decision Tree	86.65	86.66	86.65	86.66	73.28	73.30
ETC	93.64	93.64	93.64	93.64	87.27	87.28
Bagging	90.13	90.19	90.13	90.12	80.23	80.31
RF	92.73	92.74	92.73	92.73	85.45	85.46
Adaboost	90.47	90.48	90.47	90.47	80.93	80.95
Stacking Model	94.88	94.80	94.81	94.88	89.76	89.76

TABLE VII: Comparative Performance Analysis of Fine Tuned ML Models and Stacking Model for QvQ_n Leveraging Selective Features Fusion. Channel: T4REF. Dataset-FDU-64

Model	Acc	Precision	Recall	F1	Kappa	MCC
Decision Tree	83.09	82.95	83.09	83.00	62.47	62.51
ETC	90.53	90.48	90.53	90.44	78.85	78.98
Bagging	88.33	88.28	88.33	88.30	74.21	74.23
RF	90.53	90.51	90.53	90.41	78.74	78.95
Adaboost	87.92	87.84	87.92	87.86	73.19	73.24
Stacking Model	91.13	90.80	90.85	90.77	80.29	79.69

These results underscore the effectiveness of our framework in distinguishing between nuanced sleep states, which is pivotal for advancing neonatal sleep analysis and monitoring.

The integration of MMFFS helps mitigate the problem of dimensionality and enhances model interpretability. This is crucial in medical applications, where understanding the decision-making process is as critical as the decision itself. The performance gains from the stacking ensemble suggest that combining multiple learning models makes use of their individual strengths while compensating for their weaknesses. In turn, this leads to more accurate predictions. Moreover, our model's ability to operate on a reduced feature set without compromising performance makes it ideal for real-time monitoring scenarios, where computational resources and response times are critical.

A. Comparative Performance Analysis of Models using 5-Fold and LOSO-CV Techniques

Fig 4 provides a comparative analysis of model performance using two cross-validation techniques: 5-Fold-CV and LOSO-CV. In a 5-Fold-CV, the dataset is randomly divided into 5 equal-sized folds, with each fold used once as a validation set while the remaining 4 folds are used for training. This process is repeated 5 times, with each fold used as the validation set exactly once. On the other hand, LOSO-CV involves leaving out one subject from the dataset for validation while using the remaining subjects for training. This process is repeated for each subject in the dataset and requires quite a bit of validation time.

Fig. 4: Comparative Performance Analysis of Models using 5-Fold and LOSO-CV Techniques

The results depicted in Fig 4 showcase the performance metrics, specifically accuracy and Kappa, for classification tasks (“SvA” and

“ QvQ_n ”). For both classification tasks, 5-Fold-CV generally yields higher accuracy compared to LOSO. However, the difference in performance between the two techniques varies slightly depending on the classification task. For “SvA”, 5-Fold-CV achieves an accuracy of around 90% and a Kappa value of 77.51%, while LOSO yields slightly lower accuracy (89%) and kappa (74.84%). Similarly, for “ QvQ_n ”, 5-Fold-CV results in an accuracy of 91.13% and a kappa value of 79.69%, whereas LOSO produces slightly lower accuracy (89.18%) and kappa (77.13%).

The variations in performance between 5-Fold and LOSO-CV can be attributed to their differing methodologies. 5-Fold-CV involves multiple rounds of training and validation on different subsets of the data, providing a more robust estimation of model performance. In contrast, LOSO-CV leaves out one entire subject for validation in each iteration, which may lead to higher variability in performance estimation as the dataset contains subjects with significantly different characteristics. Observing these kinds of small differences makes sense due to the different techniques of validation on the dataset, which has significantly different characteristics, as mentioned in section III-B.

B. Performance

Utilizing the FDU-64 dataset on a Core i7-10750H center processing unit (CPU) reveals significant variations in execution times across different models, ranging from just a few seconds for simpler models like the ETC (37 seconds) to over seven hours for the more complex stacking model. This variation underscores a crucial balance between computational efficiency and model accuracy. Despite its lengthy execution time, the stacking model demonstrates superior accuracy and Kappa scores, indicating its enhanced predictive capability and reliability. Such a comparison highlights the essential trade-off between achieving precise and reliable predictions in neonatal sleep analysis and the computational demands required to attain these outcomes.

C. Discussion

Neonatal sleep patterns are complex and susceptible to external factors such as movement and feeding routines, so it has been challenging to analyze them. This study represents a significant advance in this field. Our study introduces innovative EEG analysis techniques that are specifically targeted to neonatal EEG data, contrasting with conventional methods focused primarily on adult data. The EEG signals of newborns differ from those of adults in terms of their amplitude and frequency, which presents unique analytical challenges. In this study, methodologies are specifically developed to accommodate these distinguishing characteristics. Our unique approaches have shown success in accurately classifying neonatal sleep states. We present a novel MMFFS as well as an ensemble stacking model for neonatal sleep classification in this study. Additionally, we proposed how data transfer to the could be reduced using the proposed approach. As compared to previous studies, the proposed methodology achieved superior results.

Future work will aim to refine the classification process so that all the stages (active sleep vs quiet sleep vs awake) of neonatal sleep can be accurately classified. Further, enhances data security by exploring data reduction techniques and utilizing edge cloud computing. To balance data accuracy and computational efficiency, we plan to experiment with different sampling frequencies, possibly with anti-aliasing filters.

VI. CONCLUSION

Our research presents a novel approach to neonatal sleep stage classification utilizing a novel MMFFS and a stacking-based ensemble classifier. It is not only more effective than previous methods, but it also has significant practical and efficiency advantages. With the proposed approach, we could simplify the data acquisition process by using fewer EEG channels, which can reduce complexity and potential discomfort for newborns. It also paves the way for more user-friendly EEG systems. With edge-based feature extraction, we can minimize processing needs and ensure cost-effectiveness by reducing data transfer to the cloud. As a result, real-time sleep pattern analysis can facilitate earlier interventions and better outcomes. Across both datasets, our approach yielded impressive results: for FDU-64, we achieved an accuracy of 90.37% and a Kappa of 77.51% for SvA states, an accuracy of 91.13% and a Kappa of 80.29% for QvQ_n, and for QvA detection, an accuracy of 94.88% and a Kappa of 89.76%. Our findings' reliability and applicability were also supported by the use of the FDU-19 dataset. There were comparable outcomes for both QvA and SvA, further confirming the validity of the proposed methodology.

REFERENCE

- [1] Muhammad Irfan, Peng Shun, Barkoum Betra Felix, Noman Mustafa, Saadullah Farooq Abbasi, Abdelwahed Nahli, Abdulhamit Subasi, Tomi Westerlund, and Wei Chen. An iot-based non-contact eeg system: Sole of the feet / hands palm. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, pages 1–1, 2023.
- [2] Muhammad Irfan, Husnain Jawad, Barkoum Betra Felix, Saadullah Farooq Abbasi, Anum Nawaz, Saeed Akbarzadeh, Muhammad Awais, Lin Chen, Tomi Westerlund, and Wei Chen. Non-wearable iot-based smart ambient behavior observation system. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 21(18):20857–20869, 2021.
- [3] Ameet S Daftary, Hasnaa E Jalou, Lori Shively, James E Slaven, and Stephanie D Davis. Polysomnography reference values in healthy newborns. *Journal of Clinical Sleep Medicine*, 15(3):437–443, 2019.
- [4] CHILDREN'S HOSPITAL OF PHILADELPHIA. Newborn-sleep patterns. April-3 -2024.
- [5] Jay Vera Summer Dr. Nilong Vyas. Sleep apnea in infants and newborns. june -2022.
- [6] Rachel Y Moon, Rebecca F Carlin, Ivan Hand, Task Force on Sudden Infant Death Syndrome, the Committee on Fetus, and Newborn. Evidence base for 2022 updated recommendations for a safe infant sleeping environment to reduce the risk of sleep-related infant deaths. *Pediatrics*, 150(1):e2022057991, 2022.
- [7] Chetan S Nayak and Arayamparambil C Anilkumar. Neonatal eeg. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing, 2021.
- [8] Saeed Montazeri Moghadam, Päivi Nevalainen, Nathan J Stevenson, and Sampsa Vanhatalo. Sleep state trend (sst), a bedside measure of neonatal sleep state fluctuations based on single eeg channels. *Clinical Neurophysiology*, 143:75–83, 2022.
- [9] Franklyn Rocha Cabrero and Orlando De Jesus. Eeg neonatal visual analysis. In *StatPearls [Internet]*. StatPearls Publishing, 2022.
- [10] Muhammad Awais, Xi Long, Bin Yin, Saadullah Farooq Abbasi, Saeed Akbarzadeh, Chunmei Lu, Xinhua Wang, Laishuan Wang, Jiong Zhang, Jeroen Dudink, et al. A hybrid dcnm-svm model for classifying neonatal sleep and wake states based on facial expressions in video. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 25(5):1441–1449, 2021.
- [11] Luay Fraiwan and Mohanad Alkhodari. Neonatal sleep stage identification using long short-term memory learning system. *Medical & Biological Engineering & Computing*, 58:1383–1391, 2020.
- [12] Emina Alickovic and Abdulhamit Subasi. Ensemble svm method for automatic sleep stage classification. *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, 67(6):1258–1265, 2018.
- [13] Ahnaf Rashik Hassan and Abdulhamit Subasi. A decision support system for automated identification of sleep stages from single-channel eeg signals. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 128:115–124, 2017.
- [14] Lan Zhuang, Minhui Dai, Yi Zhou, and Lingyu Sun. Intelligent automatic sleep staging model based on cnn and lstm. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10:2229, 2022.
- [15] Luigi Fiorillo, Alessandro Puiatti, Michela Papandrea, Pietro-Luca Ratti, Paolo Favaro, Corinne Roth, Panagiotis Bargiotas, Claudio L Bassetti, and Francesca D Faraci. Automated sleep scoring: A review of the latest approaches. *Sleep medicine reviews*, 48:101204, 2019.
- [16] Muhammad Awais, Hemant Ghayvat, and Wei chen. Face and its features detection during nap. In *2018 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Digital Signal Processing (DSP)*, pages 1–5, 2018.
- [17] Muhammad Awais, Xi Long, Bin Yin, Chen Chen, Saeed Akbarzadeh, Saadullah Farooq Abbasi, Muhammad Irfan, Chunmei Lu, Xinhua Wang, Laishuan Wang, et al. Can pre-trained convolutional neural networks be directly used as a feature extractor for video-based neonatal sleep and wake classification? *BMC research notes*, 13:1–6, 2020.
- [18] Amir H. Ansari, Kirubin Pillay, Anneleen Dereymaeker, Katrien Jansen, Sabine Van Huffel, Gunnar Nauelaers, and Maarten De Vos. A deep shared multi-scale inception network enables accurate neonatal quiet sleep detection with limited eeg channels. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 26(3):1023–1033, 2022.
- [19] Amir Hossein Ansari, Ofelie De Wel, Mario Lavanga, Alexander Caicedo, Anneleen Dereymaeker, Katrien Jansen, Jan Vervisch, Maarten De Vos, Gunnar Nauelaers, and Sabine Van Huffel. Quiet sleep detection in preterm infants using deep convolutional neural networks. *Journal of neural engineering*, 15(6):066006, 2018.
- [20] Amir H Ansari, Kirubin Pillay, Anneleen Dereymaeker, Katrien Jansen, Sabine Van Huffel, Gunnar Nauelaers, and Maarten De Vos. A deep shared multi-scale inception network enables accurate neonatal quiet sleep detection with limited eeg channels. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 26(3):1023–1033, 2021.
- [21] Rui Yu, Zhuhuang Zhou, Shuicai Wu, Xiaorong Gao, and Guangyu Bin. Mrasleepnet: a multi-resolution attention network for sleep stage classification using single-channel eeg. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 19(6):066025, 2022.
- [22] Hangyu Zhu, Yan Xu, Ning Shen, Yonglin Wu, Laishuang Wang, Chen Chen, and Wei Chen. Ms-hnn: Multi-scale hierarchical neural network with squeeze and excitation block for neonatal sleep staging using a single-channel eeg. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, pages 1–1, 2023.
- [23] Hafza Ayesha Siddiqa, Muhammad Irfan, Saadullah Farooq Abbasi, and Wei Chen. Electroencephalography (eeg) based neonatal sleep staging and detection using various classification algorithms. *CMC-COMPUTERS MATERIALS & CONTINUA*, 77(2):1759–1778, 2023.
- [24] Saadullah Farooq Abbasi, Jawad Ahmad, Ahsen Tahir, Muhammad Awais, Chen Chen, Muhammad Irfan, Hafiza Ayesha Siddiqa, Abu Bakar Waqas, Xi Long, Bin Yin, et al. Eeg-based neonatal sleep-wake classification using multilayer perceptron neural network. *IEEE Access*, 8:183025–183034, 2020.
- [25] Saadullah Farooq Abbasi, Harun Jamil, and Wei Chen. Eeg-based neonatal sleep stage classification using ensemble learning. *Comput. Mater. Contin.*, 70:4619–4633, 2022.
- [26] Awais Abbas, Saadullah Farooq Abbasi, Muhammad Zulfikar Ali, Saleem Shahid, and Wei Chen. A single channel eeg-based algorithm for neonatal sleep-wake classification. In *The International Conference of Advanced Computing and Informatics*, pages 345–352. Springer, 2022.
- [27] Muhammad Irfan, Hafza Ayesha Siddiqa, Abdelwahed Nahliis, Chen Chen, Yan Xu, Laishuan Wang, Anum Nawaz, Abdulhamit Subasi, Tomi Westerlund, and Wei Chen. An ensemble voting approach with innovative multi-domain feature fusion for neonatal sleep stratification. *IEEE Access*, 12:206–218, 2024.
- [28] Saadullah Farooq Abbasi, Qammer Hussain Abbasi, Faisal Saeed, and Norah Saleh Alghamdi. A convolutional neural network-based decision support system for neonatal quiet sleep detection. *Mathematical Biosciences and Engineering*, 20(9):17018–17036, 2023.
- [29] Arnaud Delorme and Scott Makeig. Eeglab: an open source toolbox for analysis of single-trial eeg dynamics including independent component analysis. *Journal of neuroscience methods*, 134(1):9–21, 2004.
- [30] Emrah Hancer and Abdulhamit Subasi. Eeg-based emotion recognition using dual tree complex wavelet transform and random subspace ensemble classifier. *Computer Methods in Biomechanics and Biomedical Engineering*, pages 1–13, 2022.
- [31] Mumtaz Ali, Mohsin Khan, Nguyen Thanh Tung, et al. Segmentation of dental x-ray images in medical imaging using neutrosophic orthogonal matrices. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 91:434–441, 2018.
- [32] Manual vs Automated Feature Engineering Comparison, author = Nate Parsons, journal=Github, year = 2020, url = <https://github.com/Featuretools/Automated-Manual-Comparison>.
- [33] Huy Phan and Kaare Mikkelsen. Automatic sleep staging of eeg signals: recent development, challenges, and future directions. *Physiological Measurement*, 2022.

- [34] Abdulhamit Subasi. Automatic recognition of alertness level from eeg by using neural network and wavelet coefficients. *Expert systems with applications*, 28(4):701–711, 2005.
- [35] Inan Güler and Elif Derya Übeyli. A mixture of experts network structure for modelling doppler ultrasound blood flow signals. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 35(7):565–582, 2005.
- [36] Abdulhamit Subasi. Eeg signal classification using wavelet feature extraction and a mixture of expert model. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 32(4):1084–1093, 2007.
- [37] Lokenath Debnath and Firdous Ahmad Shah. *Wavelet transforms and their applications*, volume 434. Springer, 2015.
- [38] Antonio F Pérez-Rendón and Rafael Robles. The convolution theorem for the continuous wavelet transform. *Signal processing*, 84(1):55–67, 2004.

Muhammad Irfan (Member, IEEE), is a dual-doctoral researcher affiliated with Fudan University, Shanghai, and University of Turku, Finland. Having earned a Bachelor's in Electronic Engineering from UET Taxila, Pakistan (2015), He pursued and secured a Master's in Electronics and Communication Engineering from Fudan University in 2021. He has been awarded several merit-based scholarships and fellowships, including the HEC Merit-based Scholarship, Pakistan (2012-2015), Punjab Government One Belt

One Road Scholarship (2016-2018), Chinese Government Scholarship (2018-2024), Finnish National Agency for Education Fellowship (2023-2024), FCFH Grant (May-October 2024), University of Turku Research Grant (2024-2025), and the DPT travel grant (Sept. 2024). His research spans biomedical signal processing, IoT, neonatal sleep analysis, brain tumor detection, breast cancer analysis, edge computing, and deep learning, with publications in *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, *IEEE Sensors Journal*, *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, and the Elsevier platforms.

Husnain Shahid (Member, IEEE), is a Researcher at the Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC) and is mainly involved in the European Horizon Projects. He holds a master's degree in Electronics and Communication engineering from Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China, and a bachelor's degree in Electrical (Telecommunication) Engineering from GCUF, Pakistan. His main research areas are deep learning, signal communication, and health informatics.

Abdulhamit Subasi is specialized in Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Biomedical Signal/Image Analysis and security. Concerning the application of Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning to different fields, he wrote more than 40 book chapters and more than 220 published journal and conference papers. He is the series editor of "Artificial Intelligence Applications in Healthcare & Medicine." He is also author of the books, "Practical Guide for Biomedical Signals Analysis Using Machine Learning Techniques,"

"Practical Machine Learning for Data Analysis Using Python" and the editor of the books "Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Medical Imaging", and "Advances in Non-Invasive Biomedical Signal Sensing and Processing with Machine Learning."

Chen Chen (Senior Member, IEEE) is an Associate Professor at the Human Phenome Institute in Fudan University. She received the M.S. degree in embedded system from Institut Supérieur d'Electronique de Paris (ISEP) in 2013 and the Ph.D. degree in computer science from Université Pierre et Marie Curie (UPMC) in 2016. From 2017 to 2021, she has worked as a Postdoctoral Fellow with the the Center for Intelligent Medical Electronics (CIME), School of Information Science and Technology, Fudan University. Her research interests lie in biomedical engineering, focusing on wearable sensor systems, biomedical signal processing, sleep analysis, and personalized health monitoring

Tomi Westerlund (Senior Member, IEEE), based at the University of Turku, Finland, holds a professorship in Robotics and Autonomous Systems. He leads the Turku Intelligent Embedded and Robotic Systems Research Group within the university. Professor Westerlund's primary research focuses on leveraging heterogeneous multi-robot systems (autonomous unmanned ground, aerial, and surface vehicles) in various application domains, such as environmental and infrastructure monitoring. Within these areas, his core research interests revolve around collaborative autonomy, distributed intelligence, fog/edge computing and edge AI.

Wei Chen (Senior Member, IEEE) is Head of School of Biomedical Engineering and full Professor at the University of Sydney. She received B. Eng. degree and M. Eng. degree from Xian Jiaotong University, China. She obtained her Ph.D. degree in 2007 from the University of Melbourne, Australia. She worked at Bell Laboratories Germany, Alcatel-Lucent, Stuttgart, Germany as an intern in 2005. From 2007 to 2015, she was an Assistant Professor at Eindhoven University of Technology, the Netherlands. From

2015 to 2023, she worked as a full Professor and Director of Center of Intelligent Medical Electronics at School of Information Science and Technology and Director of the Physiological Signal and Sleep platform in the Human Phenome Institute at Fudan University. She serves/served as Chair of IEEE Sensor and Systems Council China Chapter (2020-2022), Managing Editor of IEEE Reviews in Biomedical Engineering (RBME) (2020-2022), Associate Editor of IEEE transactions on Biomedical Engineering (TBME), IEEE Journal on Biomedical Health Informatics (JBHI), IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering (TNSRE), IEEE Journal of Translational Engineering in Health and Medicine (JTEHM), Editorial Board member of Phenomics and the IEEE EMBS AdCom Asia/Pacific representative.

